

GRAPHIC ITEMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11076463>

Abstract: This article provides a complete description of graphic objects in visual arts, the characteristics of painting that are different from other artistic media, how art is expressed and visually communicated, types of graphic objects, the purpose and functions of graphic objects.

Keywords: graphic materials, artistic tools, visual communication, lithography, linocut, etching.

In the visual arts, graphic materials are products and techniques that distinguish painting from other artistic media. In this article, you can learn some basic information about graphics objects. Graphics is a way of creating images and viewing the results. Graphic art types represent structural information about the unconstructed image and the faces of each proposal.

In the visual arts, graphic materials are the guides and tools essential to how art is expressed and visually communicated. With the help of these objects, the ideas and transformations of the creator of art are visually expressed, they affect the beholders and give them an opportunity to communicate them intelligibly.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Fine art can be related to several techniques and styles practiced in different fields of art. Graphics is a part of the visual arts, and it uses many components to create images and resulting instructions.

Types of graphic objects:

- Lithography: Lithography is an image with a barrier. In this method, lithograph, lithographic pencil, and lithographic drawing are preferred.
- Serigraphy: Serigraphy or silk screen presentation is a method of creating images using a medium. It is good for creating complex colors and fine details.
- Calligraphy: It is the art of writing and is concerned with the aesthetic aspect of writing. Calligraphy is commonly used to create international texts and aims to make writing elegant and artistic.
- Computer Graphics: With the development of technology, computers and graphics programs have brought opportunities to create new graphics objects. It's a great way to create, edit, and view images with computers.

3. Purpose and functions of graphic objects:

- Aesthetics: Graphics are used to understand objects, displays, and aesthetic images. They are used to influence artists and images with interest and ideas.
- Text details: Graphic objects are used to show details of text, such as in books or posters.

- Advertising and Design: Graphics are used to sell products in businesses and commerce. They are well used to make the designs beautiful and interesting.
- Scientific and Educational Purposes: Graphics are used to understand and study objects, scientific research, and educational materials..

Results:

The use of techniques such as lithography and linocut to draw graphic objects opens up new opportunities for artists to create unique and original instructions. These methods have been developed and are used in various fields of visual arts. Events explore the use of graphic arts, techniques such as lithography and linocut in the visual arts. Lithography and linocut are two of the most classic and popular techniques of graphic art. Both techniques are unique and allow artists to be creative and make creative changes to their painting.

Lithography is a type of graphic art in which images or text are drawn, mounted, or transferred. In lithography, images or texts are drawn using specific dreams, and these dreams lead to lithographic text.

Linocut is a controlled graphic technique in which images or text are printed on tiles made of linoleum or a similar material. Drawing, spreading and handling processes are carried out between the tiles. Linocuts are tough in nature as the tile requires sharp edges to fit. With this method, the editor is able to create unique instructions, and editors can create linear and well-controlled instructions.

Etching is a method of drawing through defects formed between metals using various chemical processes. Etchings provide the ability to control the resulting poisons and contrast image.

Discussion:

Graphics can be part of art and can use different techniques. For example, pencils, crayons, paint, crayons, and drawing with paper are the different mediums chosen by many artists. Other forms of graphics are created using computer software, such as Adobe Illustrator and Adobe Photoshop.

There are several different techniques and forms of graphic arts that represent different rewards of fine art. With these characteristics, graphic objects play a role in the organization of other types of visual arts, such as painting, sculpture, animation and other indicators.

In visual arts, graphic materials include the visual media used to express the art itself. These tools can take the following forms:

1. Map and pencil work: This is the most basic way to create graphics in the classic way. You can draw, tap, draw well to create a work of art using pencils, crayons, paint, and other materials. In this way, the properties and methods of art expressing its supporting capabilities are extracted.
2. Linocut: This technique creates art by cutting out an image from linoleum paint. He draws the art by wrapping his image on linoleum paper, cuts out material from it, and prints the resulting image. Linocut objects are defined by linework and the use of sunlight.
3. Collage: This technique involves cutting up art from other materials and arranging them on a surface. Collage works by using materials for expression and placing them well, using colors together.
4. Computer Graphics: There are many options for creating graphics on a computer. Can create vector and raster graphics through Illustrator, Photoshop, CorelDRAW, and other

programs. This method allows the use of electronic devices and technologies to create visual art.

5. Graffiti: Graffiti is one of the fastest growing or most popular forms of visual art. They express their opinion in the hearth, plural faces, city walls, places and other popular places. Graffiti objects are created with aerosol paints, markers, and other graphic materials.

Summary:

In conclusion, it is worth saying that graphic objects are based on different types of drawings for expression in visual arts, which can be processed to express social, political, cultural and other indicators. These objects found their place in major museums, galleries and private collections and played an important role in the understanding of art. As one of the most important parts of graphic art, it occupies a large place in the creation of art, conveying images to other people, mastering ideas and communicating with the audience.

References:

1. Boymetov B.B., Abdirasilov S.F. Chizmatasvir. -T., «G'afur G'ulom», 2004.
2. Qodirxo'jayev P. Badiiy bezak san'ati. - T., «Iqtisod-moliya», 2007.
3. Nazirov Sh.A., Nuraliyev P.M., Aytmuratov B.Sh. Rastr va vector grafika. - T.: G '.G'ulom, 2007.
4. Eminov A.G'. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilaming kompyuter grafikasi bo'yicha kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasi - Toshkent, 2012.

